

DIELECTRIC PROPERTIES OF TWO CURING EPOXY/AMINE SYSTEMS AT 2.45 GHZ

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Summary: The dielectric properties of two curing epoxy resin systems have been studied over a temperature range at 2.45 GHz. It was found that, generally, both the dielectric constant and the dielectric loss factor of the system increased with temperature and decreased as the reaction proceeded. The epoxy resins at different extents of cure exhibited the γ relaxation, which can be described by the Arrhenius Rate Law. The relaxation is attributed to the motions of the dipolar groups associated with the reactants. The Davidson-Cole model can represent the temperature dependences of the dielectric properties. The nature of the information yielded by dielectrometry on the dynamics of the system is discussed. The evolution of the parameters of the models during the polymerization was mainly affected by the decreasing number of the dipolar groups involved in the relaxation and increasing medium viscosity.

KEYWORDS: microwave, dielectric properties, epoxy resins, curing, modeling.

INTRODUCTION

Microwave processing of polymers has been studied as an attractive alternative to conventional thermal processing [1]. Dielectric properties of polymers are important for controlling microwave processing of the materials. Several empirical models were proposed to describe the dielectric properties of materials, e.g., the Debye model [2], the Davidson-Cole model [3], and the Havriliak and Negami model [4]. The diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA) epoxy resin, one of the most popular epoxy resins, has many commercial uses, e.g. adhesives, protective coatings, and electrical insulation. Studies of the dielectric behavior of DGEBA epoxy resins have received considerable attention [5-14] and three relaxations, α , β , and γ , were found. Normally, the α process randomizes the dipole moments through Brownian motion of large segments of a polymer chain and takes place at low frequencies. The β process occurs at higher frequencies and randomizes the dipole moments by reorientation of individual dipoles in the molecule chain, involving segmented motion of a smaller section of the polymer chain than the α process. The γ relaxation is the motion of individual groups of atoms in the backbone chains, e.g. epoxy groups with the DGEBA epoxy resins, at higher frequencies.

Studies on epoxy resins primarily focus on measuring dielectric properties as a function of either frequency at a constant temperature or temperature at low microwave frequencies. However, microwave heating apparatus usually operates at a constant frequency. The Federal

Communications Commission (FCC) allocated a number of microwave frequencies for Industrial, Scientific and Medical applications (ISM), among which 2.45 GHz is the major operating frequency worldwide. In order to improve industrial applications of microwave processing of epoxy resins, understanding the dielectric properties and relaxation of the reacting polymers at an industrial microwave frequency is essential. A study on the dielectric properties of DGEBA epoxy resins at different extents of cure may provide useful information for the detailed analysis of the DGEBA curing process under microwave radiation. The purpose of this paper is to analyze dielectric data of reacting epoxy resins of DGEBA and two curing agents as a function of temperature at 2.45 GHz.

EXPERIMENTAL

The epoxy prepolymer was DGEBA (DER 332 by Dow Plastics). The curing agents were a difunctional primary amine (Jeffamine D-230 by Huntsman) and *m*-phenylenediamine (mPDA by Sigma-Aldrich). The properties of DGEBA and the curing agents are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Properties of the epoxy resin and curing agents

Name	Chemical Structure	Epoxy/amine equivalent weight	Density (g/ml)
DGEBA		171-175	1.16
Jeffamine D-230		60	0.948
mPDA		27	1.14

All of the materials were used as received without further purification. In order to prepare neat DGEBA/Jeffamine epoxy resins, DGEBA was first preheated in a glass beaker at 50°C to melt any crystals present and then a stoichiometric Jeffamine (weight ratio of DGEBA : Jeffamine 2.88:1) was added. The mixture was stirred for five minutes with a magnetic bar at room temperature and degassed at 0.02 bar at room temperature for five minutes. To prepare neat DGEBA/mPDA epoxy resins, stoichiometric DGEBA and mPDA (6.4:1 by weight) were mixed in a glass beaker. The mixtures were well stirred with a magnetic bar at 65°C for five minutes and then degassed at 0.02 bar at room temperature for five minutes.

A single-frequency microwave processing and diagnostic system was used to heat epoxy resins and assess their dielectric properties. Details of the experimental equipment can be found in the literatures [15, 16]. The degassed epoxy resins were poured into a Teflon holder. The Teflon holder with a fluoroptic probe was located at the position of the highest electric field for the TM 012 cavity mode at 2.45 GHz. The DGEBA/Jeffamine fresh samples were heated to react at 90°C for specified reaction time periods (e.g. 1, 5, and 20 minutes), with the exception of those for the 0% cured epoxy resin, which were heated to 80°C. The curing temperatures for the DGEBA/mPDA system was 110°C and the peak temperatures for the

unreacted epoxy resins was 90°C. Measurements of temperature and dielectric properties using the swept frequency method were made during free convective cooling of the samples. The cooled samples were analyzed with a Differential Scanning Calorimeter to determine the residual heat of reaction per gram and, thus, the extents of cure.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The dielectric constant (ϵ') and loss factor (ϵ'') of the DGEBA/Jeffamine epoxy resin at different extents of cure vs. temperature at 2.45 GHz are presented in Fig. 1 and 2. The material's dielectric properties increase with temperature except ϵ'' at 0 and 10% extents at high temperatures and decrease as the extent of cure increases. A γ relaxation [5] was observed from the plots of ϵ'' vs. temperature in Fig. 2 at 0% and 10% extents.

Fig. 1: Temperature dependence of ϵ' at 2.45 GHz for the DGEBA/Jeffamine epoxy resins at different extents of cure (%). The curves represent the calculated data; the points represent experimental data.

Fig. 2: Temperature dependence of ϵ'' at 2.45 GHz for the DGEBA/Jeffamine epoxy resins at different extents of cure (%). The curves represent the calculated data; the points represent experimental data.

The changes in the dielectric properties of the curing DGEBA/mPDA epoxy resin at different extents of cure at 2.45 GHz are shown as plots of dielectric constant (ϵ') and loss factor (ϵ'') against temperature in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4. The material's dielectric properties increase with temperature except ϵ'' of 11% at high temperatures and decrease as the extent of cure increases. A relaxation was observed from the plots of ϵ'' vs. temperature in Fig. 4 at 11% extent. The relaxation should be the γ relaxation [5], which is the motion of individual groups of atoms, e.g. epoxy and amine groups within the curing system.

Fig. 3: Temperature dependence of ϵ' at 2.45 GHz for the DGEBA/mPDA epoxy resins at different extents of cure (%). The curves represent the calculated data; the points represent experimental data.

Fig. 4: Temperature dependence of ϵ'' at 2.45 GHz for the DGEBA/mPDA epoxy resins at different extents of cure (%). The curves represent the calculated data; the points represent experimental data.

To interpret the evolution of the dielectric properties during the curing reaction, one should know the dielectric behavior of all involved dipolar groups, which are, however, too complicated to differentiate. Epoxy resins react with stoichiometric amines via a ring-opening mechanism, shown in Fig. 5 [17]. In the first step, an epoxy group reacts with a primary

amine to form a secondary amine. In the second step, the formed secondary amine reacts with another epoxy group to produce a tertiary amine. The third step is etherification, which is reaction of a formed hydroxyl group and an epoxy group to form an ether crosslinking epoxy. However, etherification is insignificant for stoichiometric mixtures. The progress of the reaction is defined in terms of extent of cure.

Fig. 5: DGEBA epoxy resin curing mechanism

Since the dipolar groups within the reacting system and their dynamics are substantially similar, the dielectric properties of the reacting system reflect the combination of all the dipolar groups involved in the reaction. The dipolar groups involved in the γ relaxation in this study should include: epoxy and amine groups with the unreacted DGEBA and curing agents; dipolar groups with the intermediate products and final polymers, e.g. -NH- and -OH. As the reaction goes on epoxy dipoles disappear, amine dipoles change, and some new dipoles, such as hydroxyl groups, appear. Overall, the total number of the dipolar groups within the reacting system is stable. Taking into account decreasing dielectric properties during cure, it is reasonable to suppose that the contribution of different dipolar groups to the relaxation is different. The unreacted epoxy groups, -O-, and amine groups, -NH₂-, within the reaction system are the main driving forces for the apparent combined γ relaxation. The disappearance of the epoxy and amine groups during the reaction is one reason accounting for the changes of the dielectric properties. Additionally, mobility of the dipolar groups is decreasing due to the increasing viscosity of the medium during the reaction. The two reasons accounting for the decrease in the dielectric constant and loss factor during the reaction are a decrease in the number of the dipolar groups in the reactants and an increase in the viscosity.

The Davidson-Cole model was used to describe the dielectric behavior of DGEBA/Jeffamine epoxy resins [3]:

$$\begin{aligned}\varepsilon^* - \varepsilon_\infty &= \frac{(\varepsilon_0 - \varepsilon_\infty)}{(1 + j\omega\tau)^n} \\ \varepsilon' &= \varepsilon_\infty + \frac{(\varepsilon_0 - \varepsilon_\infty)\cos(n\theta)}{(1 + (\omega\tau)^2)^{\frac{n}{2}}} \\ \varepsilon'' &= \frac{(\varepsilon_0 - \varepsilon_\infty)\sin(n\theta)}{(1 + (\omega\tau)^2)^{\frac{n}{2}}} \\ \theta &= \arctan(\omega\tau)\end{aligned}\tag{1}$$

where ε^* is the complex dielectric constant; ε' is the dielectric constant, ε'' is the dielectric loss factor; j is the imaginary unit; ω ($=2\pi f$, f is the oscillator frequency in Hz) is the radial frequency of the electric field in s^{-1} ; τ is the relaxation time in s; ε_0 is the static frequency dielectric constant; ε_∞ is the high frequency dielectric constant, and n is shape parameter with a range of $0 \leq n \leq 1$.

The relaxation time in the above models is an indication of the amount of time required for a collection of dipoles in an electric field to revert to a random orientation once the field is removed. The dominant γ relaxation in this experiment should fit the Arrhenius rate law [18]

$$\tau = A \times e^{\left(\frac{E_a}{RT}\right)}\tag{2}$$

where E_a is the activation energy in J/mol, R is the gas constant in J/mol·K, T is the temperature in K, and A is the relaxation time in the high temperature limit in s.

The parameters of the Davidson-Cole model and the Arrhenius rate law, except ε_0 and A , can be calculated using the following equation [5-7]. The values of ε_0 and A were modified until the calculated data from the Davidson-Cole model fitted the experimental data well.

$$\begin{aligned}\varepsilon^* &= \varepsilon_\infty + \frac{(\varepsilon_0 - \varepsilon_\infty)}{(j\omega\tau)^n} \\ \varepsilon' &= \varepsilon_\infty + \frac{(\varepsilon_0 - \varepsilon_\infty)\cos(n\frac{\pi}{2})}{(\omega\tau)^n} \\ \varepsilon'' &= \frac{(\varepsilon_0 - \varepsilon_\infty)\sin(n\frac{\pi}{2})}{(\omega\tau)^n}\end{aligned}\tag{3}$$

Comparison of the experimental data with the calculated data is shown in Fig. 1 – Fig. 4. The difference between the experimental data and the calculated data is caused by the calculation error based on the approximation functions and the experimental error due to fluctuation of measured data including temperature, resonant frequency, and half-power frequency bandwidth.

The parameter values of the Davidson-Cole model and the Arrhenius rate law are listed in Tables 2 and 3.

Table 2: The dielectric parameters of the reacting DGEBA/Jeffamine system

Extent of cure	n	ϵ_0	ϵ_∞	$(\epsilon_0 - \epsilon_\infty)$	E_a (kJ/mol)	A (s)
0%	0.172	7.60	2.92	4.68	69	8.6E-21
10%	0.155	7.55	2.74	4.81	80	2.6E-22
18%	0.156	7.30	2.88	4.42	99	8.9E-25
30%	0.158	7.00	2.96	4.04	105	8.7E-25
38%	0.134	6.85	2.83	4.02	131	3.0E-28
47%	0.150	6.70	2.74	3.96	123	2.0E-26
63%	0.114	6.20	2.45	3.75	135	9.8E-27
82%	0.112	5.90	2.56	3.34	110	2.2E-21

Table 3: The dielectric parameters of the reacting DGEBA/mPDA system

Extent of cure	n	ϵ_0	ϵ_∞	$(\epsilon_0 - \epsilon_\infty)$	E_a (kJ/mol)	A (s)
0%	0.153	8.20	3.07	5.13	93	4.6E-24
11%	0.152	7.50	2.94	4.56	98	7.1E-25
35%	0.153	7.10	2.93	4.17	101	6.2E-25
47%	0.137	7.00	2.85	4.15	113	6.3E-26
58%	0.139	6.70	3.18	3.52	109	8.4E-25
79%	0.108	6.32	2.92	3.40	53	4.3E-14
85%	0.073	6.00	2.73	3.27	79	9.2E-16

As the reaction goes on, the parameter n decreases for the two reacting systems (see Fig. 6). The parameter n is mainly connected with the motion of dipolar groups for the secondary γ relaxation. During the reaction the motion of dipolar groups is hindered by crosslinking epoxy resins. Therefore, the parameter n decreases. $(\epsilon_0 - \epsilon_\infty)$ is the effective moment of the orienting unit. The γ relaxation strength $(\epsilon_0 - \epsilon_\infty)$ was found to decrease during the polymerization (see Fig. 7). This is consistent with the decreasing number of the dipolar groups in the reactants.

Fig. 6: n vs. extent of cure for the two reacting systems

Fig. 7: $(\epsilon_0 - \epsilon_\infty)$ vs. extent of cure

The activation energy of the γ relaxation increases during the reaction because it is more difficult for dipolar groups to relax. The phenomenon is consistent with the fact that the viscosity of the reacting system increases as the polymerization progresses. The calculated γ relaxation time has been reported as a function of the reciprocal temperature in Fig. 8 and Fig. 9. The relaxation time increases as the temperature decreases and the polymerization goes on. The main reason for the remarkable increase of the relaxation time during the reaction is the rise of the medium viscosity.

Fig. 8: Calculated τ values versus $1000/T$ for the curing DGEBA/Jeffamine system

Fig. 9: Calculated τ values versus $1000/T$ for the curing DGEBA/mPDA system

CONCLUSION

The dielectric properties of two crosslinking epoxy/amine systems as a function of temperature at 2.45 GHz have been investigated. The progress of the curing reaction is defined in terms of extent of cure. The real and the imaginary part of the complex dielectric constant decreased as the extent of cure increased. The Davidson-Cole model can be used to describe the experimental data. The Arrhenius-like dependent γ relaxation has been identified. The evolution of the parameters in the models, e.g. the shape parameter, the relaxation strength, the activation energy, and the relaxation time, can be related to the facts that the dipolar groups in the reactants decrease in number and medium viscosity increases during the polymerization.

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